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44_Car

source: (1) Braine, Jean Critchfield: Nicobarese grammar (Car dialect)
Ann Arbor, Michigan; UMI 1970; Berkeley, Univ., Diss., 1970
PL 4471 BRA 1970

/.../ hesitation juncture
/Å'/ sentence contour
/,/ macrosegment contour
/+/ word juncture

Language Profil:

Population: 30,000 (1997).
Region: North Nicobar Islands, Car Island. India
Alternate names: Pu, Car
Contact: loans from Hindi, Urdu, English, Portugese, Burmese, French
Comments: A Scheduled Tribe in India.
At least two dialects, Car and Central, are to be distinguished
Nicobarese became a written language at the end of the 19th
century

I. Morpheme Types:

i. stem

ii. preposed restricted formative

N: vocative ka- (allomorphs kə- (before unstressed syllables), ka- (elsewhere))

ex.: [kəkahé:mə] 'brother!'

V: causative ha- (allomorphs m, mi, mə, ha, ?)

ex.: /hurín/ 'be black' > /mi+hurín/ > /mirín-/ 'make black'

- also in nominal and verbal derivation

iii. postposed restricted formative

verbal inflection

ex.: thematic suffixes - form together with the verb stem the thematic stem, indicating aspect and direction

iv. preposed unrestricted formative

negation: word-level negation is formed by the occurrence of /ʔət/ before the word to be negated; occurs with verbs, predicate auxiliaries, nouns/demonstrative adverbs, numerals, and the locative

ex.: /ʔət imúh/ 'not there'
/ʔətví:ʔtu/ 'not fitted'

v. postposed un-/semi-restricted formative

- -uvə indicates possession (allomorphs uə, əuə, uə, və, u(ə), u)

N: /kahúlluvə/ 'have something to cook'

V: /ká:ʔəuə/ 'have fish'

- reflexive rɛ

occurs with verbs, possessive pronouns and indicates that the person named as possessor of the noun is the same person as the subject of the clause

II. Word

p. 32 "Phonological clues as to the presence of word juncture in a normal utterance are very few, and word juncture is highly elusive, though it is intuitively valid to the native speaker. Exact location of word juncture was not carefully worked out with the informant, and boundaries indicated here reflect immediate constituent structure."

macrosegment = consists of a sequence of words or word groups, pitch envelope, pitch register, and macrosegment-final contour; contains at least one primary or emphatic stress

III. Phonotactics (except loan words)

consonants:

- stops in syllable initial position are fortis, in syllable final position lenis and without audible release unless before a pause

- before a pause associated with a juncture stops are slightly aspirated, otherwise not

- fricatives: infrequency or non-occurrence syllable finally

- syllable finally /h/ is never preceded by a long vowel

- syllable finally /ʔ/ is always preceded by a long vowel

- /ʔ/ does not contrast with zero in word initial position and is often omitted initially in rapid speech; the pronunciation is more fortis in syllable and word final position

vowels:

- macrosegment-final vowels tend to be weakly articulated

- before syllable final /h/ vowel are exceptionally short
- long vowels vary in length: shortest length occurs when the vowel is followed somewhere in the macrosegment by a stressed syllable while the longest occurs when the vowel is immediately followed by an open syllable

IV. Syllable

- boundaries are entirely predictable:

- between adjacent vowels: [v é.ɔk] 'to grunt'
- before an intervocalic C: [la.ʔóh] 'to be broken'
- between two Cs which are intervocalic: [kúy.lə] 'prow'
- between the first and the second C of a three intervocalic sequence:
[mis.trí] 'carpenter'

- syllable canons (p.64): V(C), CV, CVC, C'V(C)

1. V(C): V = a, i, ɔ

C = k, η, l after ɔ

C = t, v after a (only two instances)

/ε/ precedes VC syllables in all instances except the interjection /ʔaí:/ 'look'
the cited examples show either syllables with a coda or if without then the V is lengthened (due to stress)

ex.: /pan.t ε.a:ka/ 'melon'

/ka.p ε.óη/ 'porpoise'

/ti. ʔε.á:t/ 'to groan'

2. syllables with onsets:

- the high mid vowels /e, ə, o/ do not occur after a nasal nor does the new phoneme /æ/ (from english loan words)

- /i/ does not occur after /ŋ/

2a) CV:

C = all consonants

V = a, ə, i, u; except *fu, *ru

- /ε/ does not occur unstressed anywhere except in /rε/ and in harmonic situations (see vowel harmony)

2b) C'VC²:

C¹ = all C except r, v

C² = all C except f, s, ʔ, r

V = a, ə, i, u

- „not all possibilities generated by this formula have been found to occur” (p. 67)

- systematic restrictions:

- /i/ does not occur before a labial consonant unless juncture follows
- /p, f/ do not occur before /un/, i.e. *pun, *fun

- in addition to the above CVC syllables /ɔ/, /e/ each occur in a handful of weak stressed CVC syllables, most of which are contractions

ex.: [p ɔc] < /pó:ʔ əc/ 'because I'
[p ɔm] < /pó:ʔ əm/ 'because you (sg.)'

2c) C¹Ŵ(C²):

C¹ = all C except for the general restrictions already mentioned

V = all V

C² = all C except /r, r/

- restrictions:

- /f/ occurs syllable finally in only one word – probably a loan

- /n/ does not occur syllable finally after a long V

- /ʔ/ is always preceded by a long V when syllable final

- the following combinations do not occur in the data: {e, i}p; ə{h, ʔ}; ey; {u, ə, ε}v

- as a result of both vowel harmony and metathesis, the consonants /l, ɲ, ŋ, v, y/ occur syllable finally after all vowels except /ə, æ/ in unstressed syllables beginning with a laryngeal

V. Phonological Processes

i. Rules not defined according to stress

a) /c/ > [tʃ] / _V

applies „usually“ (p. 42)

b) glide insertion:

epenthetic vocalic palatal glide [i] occurs following a vowel before the palatal consonants /c/, /ɲ/ when they are syllable final

c) vowel nasalization

slightly nasalized allophones in the following environment:

1. in an unstressed closed syllable beginning with /ʔ/ or /h/ and ending with a nasal; ex.: /humlúm/ > [hũmlúm] 'gold'

2. after a nasal when neither /ʔ/ or /h/ follows; ex.: /malá:kə/ > [mãlá:kə] 'citron'

d) Backening of /a/: /a/ > [ɑ] / k_

ii. Rules pertaining to syllables preceding stressed syllables

a) Vowel Loss

the first of two adjacent unstressed vowels is lost: ǃ > Ø / _ǃ

ex.: /kain rí:r/ > [kinrí:r] 'cooking utensils'

/siinró:lə/ > [sin ró:lə] 'butting'

b) Vowel Assimilation

unstressed /i/ and /i:/ assimilate to a following labial consonant that is not before juncture:

ĩ, ĩ > ü / _L(-+)

ex.: /k imhí:t/ > [kumhí:t] 'one who fishes'

/kimyún/ > [kumyún] 'soldier'

c) Vowel Assimilation

unstressed /ə/ assimilates to a following unstressed vowel when a laryngeal intervenes:

ǎ > V' / _ HV'

ex.: /mə ʔiyén/ > [miʔiyén] 'inhabitants'

d) Dissimilation

- one of the two consonants in the sequence /hǎh/ dissimilates to [ʔ]:

/hǎh/ > [hǎ ʔ] ~ [ʔǎh] / _V' (free variation)

ex.: /mahahó:r/ > [ma ʔahó:r] ~ [mahaʔó:r] 'one who drives (something) away'

- /h/ before /af/ or /as/ dissimilates to [ʔ]: /h/ > [ʔ] / _ǎ{f, s} V'

ex.: /hafál/ > [ʔafál] 'to cause to run'

/has éh/ > [ʔaséh] 'to cause to be overcooked'

e) Glottal Stop Prothesis

ʔ is introduced before an initial vowel: Ø > ʔ / +_V

ex.: /an/ > [ʔan] 'he (subj., non-past, vis.)'

f) Unstressed VH loss

sequence vowel-laryngeal is lost before another unstressed vowel in a closed syllable: ṼH > Ø / _ ṼC

ex.: /mu ʔumfó:v/ > [mumfó:v] 'one who makes (something) cold'

iii. Rules pertaining to stressed syllables and syllables following stressed syllables
rules are fairly strictly ordered

a) Vowel Lowering

a mid vowel becomes a lower mid vowel after a nasal or a cluster of nasal plus /h/ :

/e, o, ə/ > [ɛ, ɔ, ə] / N(h)_

ex.: kané:tə/ > [kan é:tə] 'the binding together'

b) h Loss

h is lost before /ʔ/: h > Ø / _ ʔ

ex.: /ɲíh ʔa/ > [ɲíʔa] 'this.INAM.SPEC'

c) Vowel Lengthening

a stressed vowel in an open syllable is long unless the next syllable begins with a laryngeal

ex.: /f ɛlə/ > [fɛ:lə] 'be killed'

- in slow speech a vowel before /h/ is sometimes lengthened

d) Assimilation: vowel nasalization

long vowel after a nasal is nasalized: V > Ṽ / N_:

ex.: /pumná:mə/ > [pumnã:mə] 'a village'

e) Length Loss

Length is lost before glottal stop when a vowel follows:

: > ø / _ ʔV

ex.: /lú: ʔə/ > [lúʔə] 'be chased'

sometimes this rule does not apply in slow speech

f) /r/ loss

lost before a consonant or juncture

/r/ > ø / _ {C, +}

ex.: /ʔasé:r/ > [ʔasé:] 'to pour'

g) „Prestoppage”

a nasal as a syllable coda to a stressed oral vowel has a homorganic, voiced, lenis prestoppage (this oral component is shorter in duration than the nasal stop)

ex.: /kúm/ > [kúbm] 'to bring'

iv. Rules pertaining to syllables following stressed syllables

a) Metathesis

a sequence /Rə/ (where R is any of /l, m, n, ŋ, ɲ/ or a V) is metathesized after a laryngeal

/Rə/ > [əR] / H_

- this rule is optional when the segments to which it pertains are in word-final position; otherwise it is obligatory

ex.: /rúhlə/ > [rúhəl] 'to move up'

b) Semivowel rule

unstressed /i/ and /u/ become /y/ and /v/ after a vowel

ĩ, ũ > y, v / V_

ex.: hó: ʔəu > hó:ʔəv 'be agreeable'

c) Glide (semivowel) insertion

semivocalic glides y and v are introduced between /iə/ and /uə/
ex.: /hó:luə/ > [hó:luvə] 'have a friend'

d) Vowel Loss

an unstressed vowel is lost following an unstressed vowel with an intervening consonant other than /t/ or /r/

$V > \emptyset / VC\{-t, r\} _$

ex.: /ɲáθhaka/ > [ɲáθhak] 'to be bound'

e) schwa assimilation

/ə/ is totally assimilated to a preceding stressed vowel when a laryngeal intervenes

$\text{ə} > V^1 / \acute{V}^1 H _$

Vowel length blocks this rule

often this rule does not operate in slow speech or when V^1 is /i/ or /u/

ex.: /fóhəyə/ > [fóhoyə] 'be driven out'

f) Nasalization Loss

if identical vowels are separated by glottal stop and the first of those vowels is nasalized and stressed, the nasalization is lost

$\tilde{V}^1 > V^1 / \acute{A}L _ \text{?}V^1$

ex.: /lú?ũ/ > [lú?ũ] 'be chased'

g) assimilation - nasalization

a tonic or posttonic vowel is nasalized if there is a nasal in the preceding syllable and a laryngeal intervenes

$V > \tilde{V} / N(V)H _$

ex.: /mahú:və/ > [mahú:və] 'a wave'

v. Rule pertaining to segments between stressed syllables

Loss unstressed /ər/ between stressed vowels

$/\text{ər}/ > \emptyset / \acute{V}(C) _ \acute{V}$

ex.: /pó:ytər ó:ʔ/ > [pó:ytó:ʔ] 'be great (of sound)'

VI. Stress

- three contrastive degrees: primary /´/, weak, emphatic /´´/

- weak stress: irrelevant to environmental statements of strong stress variation

- primary stress /´/ occurs in three variants: primary [´], secondary [˘], tertiary [˘˘]

(the unit for this allophony to which the grammar refers is the macrosegment)

a) tertiary stress occurs between primary stresses

ex.: /tis ókɲə kúy kinló:ɲə cin./ > [tisòɲə kúy kinló:ɲə cin..Á´]

'I jumped over the fence'

b) primary stress occurs macrosegment-finally when no emphatic stress occurs in the macrosegment

ex.: /ku ríŋtɛn cɔ́: cin,Á´/ > [kurɪŋtɛ̃n cɔ́: cin..Á´]
'I push John down'

c) secondary stress occurs elsewhere:

- macrosegment initially (if another /ÁL/ or /ÁLÁL/ occurs in the macrosegment)

ex.: /k ihí:ə kú:ʔ cin, ná:ʔ,Á´/ > [k ihí:ə kú:ʔ cinÁ´ ná:ʔ.. Á´]
no translation!

- macrosegment finally when preceded by /ÁLÁL/ (only one instance observed)

ex.: /héh kíht é̃n, ʔín kɔl/ > [hèŋ kíhtè ʔín kɔl]
'There is only one problem (facing) us'

- every macrosegment has at least one primary or emphatic stress. If none of the morphemes of the macrosegment is inherently stressed, macrosegmental primary stress occurs on the first syllable

- emphatic stress stands in a one to one relationship with a single morpheme and it normally occurs with all expletives, but it may also occur with any primary stressed morpheme to draw attention to it

ex.: /kapǎh cin./ > [kapǎh cin..Á´]

'I am dead!'; equivalent to 'My god!' (surprise)

V. Infixes

- in derivation

- occur with stems having either the shape CVC or CVCVC, and are infixated according to rules:

- with stems having the shape CVC, the infix has the shape VC and occurs after the initial consonant

ex.: /f é:l/ + /-am-/ > /famé:l/ 'killer'

/t í:c/ + /-ah-/ > /tahí:c/ 'what is planted'

- with stems having the shape CVCVC, the infix has the shape C and occurs after the initial CV

ex.: /kul éh/ + /-n-/ > /kunléh/ 'what is thrown'